

Variation of Biologically Active Compounds in Three Introduced *Dracocephalum moldavica* L. Varieties under the Valley Conditions of Armenia

Alvina Avagyan

Scientific Centre of Vegetable and Industrial Crops, Armenia

Jan Brindza

*Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra,
Institute of Plant and Environmental Sciences, Slovak Republic*

Vladimíra Horčinová Sedláčková

*Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra,
Institute of Plant and Environmental Sciences, Slovak Republic*

Laura Tadevosyan

Scientific Centre of Vegetable and Industrial Crops, Armenia

Gayane Martirosyan

Scientific Centre of Vegetable and Industrial Crops, Armenia

Margarita Harutyunyan

*Scientific Center of Agrobiotechnology,
Armenian National Agrarian University, Armenia*

Marina Hovhannisyan

*Scientific Center of Agrobiotechnology,
Armenian National Agrarian University, Armenia*

Abstract

This study investigates the variation in biologically active compounds among three introduced varieties of *Dracocephalum moldavica* L. – ‘Gorynych’, ‘Moldavia’, and ‘Ametist’ - cultivated under the valley conditions of Armenia. Total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), and phenolic acid levels were determined to evaluate their nutritional and functional potential. The results demonstrated clear differences among the varieties. ‘Gorynych’ showed the highest concentrations of TPC (45.2 mg gallic acid equivalents per gram dry weight, GAE/g DW), TFC (27.1 mg quercetin equivalents per gram dry weight, QE/g DW), and phenolic acids (30.5 mg caffeic acid equivalents per gram dry weight, CAE/g DW), followed closely by ‘Ametist’ and ‘Moldavia’. These compounds are known for their antioxidant properties, contributing to the functional value of the plant material. The study represents a novel contribution, as most existing research focuses on wild populations of *D. moldavica*, while data on introduced cultivated varieties are lacking. The findings underline the importance of expanding agrobiodiversity by introducing promising species and varieties, particularly in the context of developing climate-resilient crops and functional foods. This research supports the strategic use of introduced plants to enhance food security and nutritional quality in Armenia.

Keywords: *Moldavian dragonhead, bioactive compounds, functional food.*

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Introduction

The enhancement of agrobiodiversity plays a critical role in promoting sustainable food systems, ensuring food security, and strengthening resilience to climate change. In addition to the conservation and cultivation of traditional landraces, the enrichment of agrobiodiversity through the introduction and adaptation of new plant species and varieties is increasingly recognized as a strategic approach to support agricultural diversification and nutritional improvement (Nepali et al., 2024, McCord et al. 2015). Among such species, *Dracocephalum moldavica* L., commonly known as Moldavian dragonhead, has attracted attention due to its high content of biologically active compound (Moldovan et al., 2022, Agati et al., 2012). These compounds contribute to the plant's functional properties, making it valuable for food, medicinal, and nutraceutical applications (Samtiya et al., 2021). While there is a growing body of research on wild forms of *D. moldavica*, studies focusing on introduced cultivars are limited, the introduced varieties cultivated in Armenia have not been previously characterized for their content of biologically active compounds. This study represents the first comparative evaluation of three introduced varieties, providing new insights into their phytochemical profiles. By characterizing the total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), and individual phenolic acids, this work aims to contribute to a better understanding of the nutritional and functional value of *D. moldavica* varieties supporting their future use in breeding, cultivation, and product development.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material

Three varieties of *Dracocephalum moldavica* L. – ‘Gorynych’, ‘Moldavia’, and ‘Ametist’ - were cultivated under the agroecological conditions of the Ararat Valley, Armenia on the experimental plot of the Scientific Centre of Vegetable and Industrial Crops (SCVIC). Standard agronomic practices appropriate for aromatic and medicinal plants were followed throughout the growing season. The accessions of the Genebank of the SCVIC were used for the experiments carried out (Avagyan et al., 2020).

Sample Preparation

Leaves and flowering tops were harvested at full flowering stage. The plant material was air-dried at room temperature in a shaded, well-ventilated area, ground to a fine powder, and stored in airtight containers protected from light until analysis.

Extraction Procedure

For all assays, 0.5 g of powdered plant material was extracted with 25 mL of 70% ethanol by shaking at room temperature for 24 hours. The extracts were filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper before analysis.

Determination of Total Phenolic Content

Total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method (Pérez et al., 2023). 0.5 mL of extract was mixed with 2.5 mL of 10% Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and 2 mL of 7.5% sodium carbonate solution. After incubation at room temperature for 30 minutes in the dark, absorbance was

measured at 765 nm using a Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. TPC was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE) per gram of dry weight.

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content (TFC) was determined by the aluminum chloride colorimetric method (Shraim et al., 2021). 0.5 mL of extract was mixed with 0.5 mL of 2% aluminum chloride solution. After 30 minutes of incubation at room temperature, absorbance was measured at 415 nm. Results were expressed as milligrams of quercetin equivalents (mg QE) per gram of dry weight.

Estimation of Phenolic Acids

Total phenolic acids were estimated spectrophotometrically by Arnov's method (Czigle et al., 2022). 1 mL of extract was mixed with 1 mL of 0.5 M HCl, 1 mL of Arnov's reagent, and 1 mL of 1 M NaOH. Absorbance was read at 490 nm. The content of phenolic acids was expressed as milligrams of caffeic acid equivalents (mg CAE) per gram of dry weight.

Statistical Analysis

All analyses were performed in triplicate. The results are presented as mean values \pm standard deviation (SD). ANOVA statistical method was applied.

Results

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content (TPC) of *Dracocephalum moldavica* varieties showed noticeable variation (see Figure 1). Among the three varieties, 'Gorynych' exhibited the highest TPC value (45.2 mg GAE/g DW), followed by 'Ametist' (42.5 mg GAE/g DW) and 'Moldavia' (40.8 mg GAE/g DW). Phenolic compounds are well known for their strong antioxidant properties, which contribute to the plant's defence mechanisms and enhance the functional value of plant-based foods. Higher TPC levels suggest a greater potential for antioxidant activity and possible applications in functional foods and nutraceuticals.

Figure 1. Total Phenolic Content in *D. moldavica* Varieties (mg GAE/g DW)

Total Flavonoid Content

The total flavonoid content (TFC) results revealed a similar trend. 'Gorynych' presented the highest TFC (27.1 mg QE/g DW), while 'Ametist' and 'Moldavia' had slightly lower values - 26.0 and 24.5 mg QE/g DW, respectively (see Figure 2). Flavonoids, a major subclass of phenolic compounds, are recognized for their multiple biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects.

Varieties with elevated TFC may offer enhanced health-promoting benefits and wider potential for food and pharmaceutical applications.

Figure 2. Total Flavonoid Content in *D. moldavica* Varieties (mg QE/g DW)

Phenolic Acids Content

Regarding phenolic acids, the varieties showed moderate differences. ‘Gorynych’ again demonstrated the highest content (30.5 mg CAE/g DW), whereas ‘Moldavia’ and ‘Ametist’ exhibited values of 28.7 and 27.2 mg CAE/g DW, respectively.

Phenolic acids, such as rosmarinic acid and caffeic acid, play an important role in neutralizing free radicals and contribute to the overall bioactivity of medicinal and aromatic plants. Variations in phenolic acid content between varieties may influence their functional qualities and their suitability for specific uses in food, health, or cosmetic industries.

Figure 3. Phenolic Acids Content in *D. moldavica* Varieties (mg CAE/g DW)

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate notable variability in the total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), and phenolic acid concentrations among the three *Dracocephalum moldavica* cultivars introduced and cultivated under the conditions of the Ararat Valley. These differences may reflect both genetic characteristics and environmental influences specific to the region.

Among the cultivars, ‘Gorynych’ exhibited the highest TPC, and phenolic acid content, while ‘Ametist’ and ‘Moldavia’ showed relatively lower levels. The TFC values were moderately higher in ‘Gorynych’ and ‘Ametist’ compared to ‘Moldavia’. These findings are in line with previously reported data for *D. moldavica* grown in various agroecological zones, where TPC typically ranges between 35–55 mg GAE/g DW and TFC between 20–30 mg QE/g DW. The observed values in the Ararat Valley fall within this range, suggesting an acceptable adaptation of the introduced cultivars to local conditions.

Environmental factors likely played a role in shaping the phenolic profile of the plants. The Ararat Valley is characterized by a hot, dry climate with intense sunlight and relatively low precipitation during the summer months. These conditions are known to affect the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, including phenolic compounds. Studies have shown that moderate drought stress can induce the accumulation of phenolics and flavonoids as part of the plant’s defense mechanisms (Chaves et al., 2009), while excessive heat may suppress enzymatic pathways involved in their production (Jaakola & Hohtola, 2010). Furthermore, increased UV radiation under high solar intensity may enhance flavonoid synthesis, as these compounds help protect plant tissues from oxidative damage (Agati et al., 2012). The combination of drought, high temperature, and UV exposure characteristic of the Ararat Valley may have contributed to the variability in phenolic compound levels observed among the cultivars. In this context, the relatively high TPC and TFC values in ‘Gorynych’ and ‘Ametist’ suggest a favorable response to environmental stress and highlight their potential as valuable sources of bioactive compounds for functional food applications.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of *Dracocephalum moldavica* as valuable sources of bioactive compounds for functional food applications, with cultivars displaying varying concentrations of total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and phenolic acids. The environmental conditions of the Ararat Valley, particularly its hot, dry climate, appear to influence the accumulation of these compounds, with moderate drought and high solar radiation potentially enhancing biosynthesis in certain cultivars.

The results underscore the importance of both genetic variation and environmental factors in shaping the phytochemical profile of plants. Cultivars such as ‘Gorynych’ and ‘Ametist’ have shown promising levels of bioactive substances and may be well-suited for further cultivation and selection in the region. These findings contribute to the broader goal of enriching agrobiodiversity through the introduction of new species and varieties, promoting the cultivation of plants that not only enhance food security but also offer functional benefits to human health. The introduction and adaptation of such species in Armenia’s arid regions, such as the Ararat Valley, represents a promising step towards building a more diversified, climate-resilient agricultural system. Further studies should focus on optimizing cultivation practices, exploring seasonal variations in phytochemical content, and assessing the long-term effects of environmental stress on plant metabolism.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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